

Performance Indicators Labor in the Sector of Tourism

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Abstract: This article examines the labor productivity of tourism workers, labor productivity in valuation, labor productivity in physical terms, a comprehensive indicator of the dynamics of labor efficiency, measured by the ratio of revenue from the sale of a tourism product to the average number of employees for the corresponding period.

Keywords: Tourism, hotels, efficiency, labor productivity, business.

Uzbekistan, as one of the key countries on the Great Silk Road, with a centuries-old history, unique culture and traditions, is attracting increasing attention from foreign travel companies and tourists. For example, on July 9-10 this year, a meeting of the CIS Council on Tourism was held in Samarkand, and Samarkand also became a member of the world Federation of Tourist Cities (WTFC).

The benefits provided to foreign investors and entrepreneurs in Uzbekistan, especially in the field of international tourism, have attracted the attention of both large hotel chains and small hotel management companies.

An analysis of the current state of the tourism system shows that there is an increase in the main indicators of tourism, as a consequence of the drastic measures taken to reform the industry, reconstruct the material and technical base and improve services for tourists. This can be seen from the data on the reception of tourists for the period of 10 months in 2023.

Table 1. Dynamics of growth in tourist reception in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 10 months of 2023

Months	Reception of tourists by year, people.		Change, %	Deviation from the average, +/-	
	2022	2023		2022	2023
January	266194	437265	164.26	-175738	-122426
February	264392	393493	148.83	-177540	-166198
March	441134	549454	124.55	-798	-10237
April	434962	544386	125.16	-6970	-15305
May	441500	496751	112.51	-432	-62940
June	472907	613475	129.72	30975	53784
July	506105	597665	118.09	64173	37974
August	584434	692271	118.45	142502	132580
September	503305	613784	121.95	61373	54093
October	504390	658366	130.53	62458	98675
Total	4419323	5596910	129.4	-	-

The table is compiled according to data from the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan fortourism, www.uzbektourism.uz.

From the above data we can conclude that tourism is developing at a high rate in our country. So, over the 10 months of this year, the number of people entering Uzbekistan amounted to about 4,420 thousand people, which is 29.4% more than for the same period in 2022. At the same time, the country will remain significantly influenced by the seasonality factor. Thus, in the first two months under review, there is a large difference from the average indicators. In 2023, even in May, the deviation from the average is about 63 thousand people.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 5, 2019, No. UP-5611 "On additional measures for the accelerated development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan" The Concept for the development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019 - 2025 was approved, which provides for the development of tourism infrastructure and the formation of an accessible and comfortable tourist environment.

The development of the tourism industry is directly related to the need to increase labor productivity in the industry and improve the efficiency of use of human resources. This is due to the high labor intensity of tourism services and the share of human labor in organizing tourist services.

As you know, a general indicator of the efficiency of using labor is labor productivity. In a broad sense performance labor is its effectiveness, that is, a maximum of labor products with a minimum of labor costs. Labor productivity is determined by the quantity of products (material goods, services) produced and sold per unit of time, or by the inverse value - the quantity time spent on the production and sale of a unit of product. Thus, labor productivity - This is the degree of efficiency of the purposeful activity of people, reflecting the ability to produce a certain volume of use values per unit of working time. The complexity and significance of the category of labor productivity attracts many domestic and foreign economists. Currently, many different definitions of labor productivity have been proposed, which reflect various aspects of the use of human resources and the specifics of economic sectors.

At the same time, about The definition of labor productivity for the tourism and hospitality sector has not yet been sufficiently reflected in the literature. In addition, labor productivity indicators for enterprises in this industry are not entirely accurately and completely presented.

Labor productivity of tourism workers can have three indicators:

- labor productivity in valuation;
- labor productivity in physical terms;
- a comprehensive indicator of labor efficiency dynamics.

Labor productivity in valuation is the output of workers of a tourism enterprise. It is measured by the ratio of revenue from the sale of a tourism product to the average number of employees for the corresponding period. For example, labor productivity in physical terms shows how many tourists are served by one average employee of a tourism enterprise or company. It is measured by the ratio of the number of tourists to the average number of workers.

However, these indicators by themselves cannot characterize the intensity of labor. They need to be compared with the output of the previous period, that is, to obtain indices that characterize the dynamics. The above indicators of labor productivity may have different trends and directions of change, which are caused by factors independent of a person's labor activity (changes in prices, tariffs, an increase in the number of tourists buying tours at discounted prices, etc.). Therefore, to objectively assess the dynamics of labor productivity of tourism industry workers, it is used a comprehensive indicator of labor efficiency dynamics, which means the level of efficiency in the use of labor in this industry. It represents the geometric mean value of the product of the change indices of the two indicators discussed above, calculated for the same period.

The specificity of labor in the hotel business is that labor productivity largely depends on the size of the tourist flow, that is, on the seasonality of the tourism business. In this case, productivity does not depend on the qualifications and abilities of the employee. For the same reason, the

hotel enterprise is limited in the rate of growth of labor productivity. We believe that labor productivity indicators should be divided into two large groups:

Indicators of labor costs, that is, indicators characterizing labor costs for servicing a hotel over a certain period of time. This group of indicators includes the level of use of full-time employees for the reporting period, the length of the working week, the presence and use of temporary (seasonal) employees, planned and actual time per employee, the ratio of working and administrative personnel, etc.;

Labor intensity indicators that characterize the level of use of human resources. This group includes such indicators as the number of person-days or overnight stays served, cost indicators per employee, average length of stay of tourists, volume of services provided per employee, etc.

The first group reflects the volume of the enterprise's need for human resources and the structure of labor costs, while the second group assesses the nature of the use of human resources.

The use of this approach helps to increase the objectivity and reliability of assessment indicators, which will allow the development of real measures to increase labor productivity. Scientifically and methodologically, it is necessary to deeply study the external and internal factors that influence labor productivity.

Increasing labor efficiency is greatly influenced by the rhythm of the hotel's work and the increase in the volume of sales of services. This influence occurs in two ways. Firstly, increasing the rhythm and volume of sales of services helps to reduce interruptions in work and thereby increase labor intensity, and secondly, the number of administrative personnel is increasing at a slower pace than the overall growth in revenue from the sale of tourism services, that is, the ratio of working and administrative personnel will change in favor of the former.

We believe that the use of proposals for improving the assessment of labor productivity will contribute to the development of ways to increase the efficiency of labor resources in tourism enterprises.

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